

TESTING BASEPAPERS AND IT'S COMPONENTS WITH THERMAL DECOMPOSITION TO CLASSIFY CORRUGATED CARDBOARDS FROM QUALITY ASPECTS

Barnabás Tóth¹, László Koltai², Julianna Tósi³, Péter Böröcz³

¹Doctoral School on Materials Sciences and Technologies, Óbuda University,
Budapest, Hungary

²Rejtő Sándor Faculty of Light Industry and Environmental Protection
Engineering, Óbuda University, Budapest, Hungary

³Department of Logistics and Forwarding, Széchenyi István University,
Győr, Hungary

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toth.barnabas@phd.uni-obuda.hu

Abstract: *Identifying and knowing the suitable paper quality for various packaging structures is an element process in the packaging industry involving the paper manufacturers, more involved corrugated paperboards manufacturing. The basepapers are the most essential base component of paperboards produced from wood origin components. The organic substances components of the constituent of corrugated cardboards are appropriate for thermo-analytical studies. The quality of the base-papers mainly defined by the content of primer cellulose, recycled paper and other incrust materials. At the same time, it is difficult to precisely separate base papers that exhibit differences in mechanical and quality properties, as their ulterior identification is virtually impossible. The testing methods such as CCT, RCT, FCT, COBB, bursting etc. are supported by statistical technique from mechanical properties point of view, but do not provide perfectly accurate results in terms of quality. In this paper we present a novel thermoanalytical identifaciton technique on basepapers, which based on determination of different components of wood, paper, biomasses and pure cellulose. Applying Differential Scanning Calorimetries (DSC) method, it is possible to study endotherm and exotherm*

spectrums of each constituents, which are mainly influenced by thermal decomposition of the cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and other incrust or adcrust materials. Measuring and understanding the chemical behaviour of the components under thermal test processes, can refer to mechanical properties of corrugated boards too. These cellulose and extenders content can be analyzed by the help of typify curve ranges showing chemical processes. The results show that this method on one hand can be helpful to test in a phase of production corrugated cardboards, on the other hand can help to explain properly quality issues after using the finished packaging by classifying base paper types in a simple and transparent manner.

Key words: corrugated cardboard, basepaper, cellulose, thermo-analytical technique, heatflow, DSC, chemical bonds

1 INTRODUCTION

Knowing the organic substances components of basepapers, mainly cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, other incrust materials and extenders which constitute a complex chemical system can give scope for Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) as part of the thermo-analytical measurements. (S.Soares, G.Camin, S.Levchik, 1995.) The thermo-analytical scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyzers allow the identification of each substance according to its natural origins which behaves on different ways during the test. Physical and chemical properties of each component can paraphrase accurately the investigated paper, independently from the condition of papers and effects of the environment on it (Robertson, 1993; Caulfield, Daniel, and Gunderson., 1988).

2 THERMONALITICAL DSC METHOD

Using a DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry) apparatus is one of the types of Thermoanalytical test methods. The DSC measures the physical and chemical changes of the sample material as a function of temperature. The thermal analysis provides information for the typify temperature peaks, which refer to characterization changes for each component. On the other hand derivative values proportional to the quantity of the transformed material, can be obtained. (Haines, 2012, Tóth, Koltai and Böröcz , 2018)

The method based on energy changes which can be monitored occurring in a given component during the heating and temperature keeping or cooling period. The test can measure the heat flow differences between the sample

and the reference jars due to absorbed and released heat in function of temperature. In the most widespread DSC equipment a constant heating rate is used, and the heat flow differential between the sample and the reference material is registered as a temperature differential ratio. The formula (1) for the measure heat flow is shown below:

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = C_p \frac{dT}{dt} + f(T, t) \quad (1)$$

where dH/dt is DSC heat flow signal

C_p is a sample heat capacity (heat specific x weight)

dT/dt is heating rate

$f(T,t)$ is heat flow that function of time at an absolute temperature (kinetic)

During the test a differential thermal analysis curve of the sample is recorded, where the abscissa represents temperature or time, with the heat flow (set according to the exothermic or endothermic nature of the change) shown on the ordinate. Figure x shows the characteristic curve of a base paper. The temperature at which a transformation takes place (initial temperature) is shown by the intersection of the extension of the base line and the tangent to the inflexion point. The conclusion of the temperature-dependent transformation is shown by the peak of the curve. The enthalpy of the transformation is proportional to the area between the curve and the baseline (the correct ratio can be defined through measuring a known material). Through the post- measurement analysis the temperature interval, peak temperature, heat flow, and heat in ratio of mass for the transformation can be expressed. (Tóth, Koltai and Böröcz ,2018.)

3 MEASUREMENT CIRCUMSTANCES AND ANALYSIS

During the experiments we tested parallelly min. 5-5 samples of three different basepapers, filler materials (Kaolin, CaCO_3) and cotton which are consumed for mainly mass production of corrugated cardboards.

Table 1: Tested materials list with specific properties.

Tested material	Source	Content
<i>Pure Cotton</i>	<i>Natural cotton treated with NaOH</i>	<i>Cellulose</i>
<i>Kraftliner base paper</i>	<i>Pine treated by sulphite method</i>	<i>Cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin & inorganic components</i>
<i>Testliner basepaper</i>	<i>Pine treated by sulphate method</i>	<i>Cellulose, recycled cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin & inorganic components</i>
<i>Filler material I.</i>	<i>Mined minerals</i>	<i>Kaolin</i>
<i>Filler material II.</i>	<i>Mined Minerals</i>	<i>CaCO₃</i>

Test procedure steps:

1. Preparation of test samples 8-20 mg sample take place in 30 µl jar, which exact weight measure with precision mg weight measurement apparatus.
2. A reference jar and a jar filled with the sample have to be placed into the Setaram DSC measuring device.
3. A predefined test program have to be performed.
4. Using nitrogen purge during examination.
 - a. Heating the test chamber of the measuring device to 30 °C and keeping it at this temperature for 10 minutes.
 - b. Heating the test chamber up to 540 °C at a rate of 10K/min.
 - c. Recording temperature differentials between the sample to be examined and the reference jar.
 - d. Analyzing the data on the basis of peak temperatures and heat flow.
5. Performing the measurement on 5 samples per base paper and presenting the results obtained and their averages graphically.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the literatures, the shape of the sample curves, the exothermic and endothermic reactions marked with temperature peaks paired with the heatflow values mainly influenced by the three constituents (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) (Tóth , Koltai and Böröcz P., 2018). At each

components of basepapers are produced significant differences. The degradation of hemicellulose begins at 220 °C and has its end at 315 °C. In case of cellulose the process takes place between 315 and 400 °C on higher temperature. Lignin produces exothermic and endothermic reactions under the whole experimental interval and it can be extended up to 900 °C. At lower temperature first the lignin and the hemicellulose begin to decompose. Regarding the researches in the literature, the first decomposition reactions are occurred by the C-C and C-O bonds rupture of hemicellulose. The process results a pyrolysis reaction with higher heatflow values. The special characteristic of high primer cellulose content samples are shown by the decomposition of carbonil (C-O-C) and carboxil (C=O) groups of cellulose and hemicellulose between 280 °C and 500 °C.

Table 2: The result of examined samples by DSC

a) NaOH treated cotton

b) Kraftliner basepaper

c) Testliner basepaper

d) Kaolin and CaCO₃

The sample specific curves are produced by its components specific results. The curves are shown different temperature peaks at exothermic and endothermic reactions, which help to identify the local minimum and maximum points on the curves. Another key feature of decomposition processes are the heat flow values (Hf), which explain and characterize various thermal processes in the sample.

Figure 1: Cotton sample DSC curve (local minimum and maximum points marked with red points)

On the 1. Figure can be seen the basis of the parallel measurement results. The temperature peaks of the characteristic processes were marked. The following points belong to the local minimum and maximum places on the curves. At each local places on the curves were defined by it's heatflow (mW) and T_{max} or T_{min} ($^{\circ}C$) values.

Table 3: DSC results of Cotton, Kraftliner and Testliner basepaper samples

Reaction type	Endotherm		Exotherm		Endotherm		Exotherm		Endotherm		Exotherm	
Sample	I. Local min.		VI. Local max.		III. Local min.		VI. Local max.		V. Local min.		VI. Local max.	
	T_{min} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)	T_{max} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)	T_{min} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)	T_{max} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)	T_{min} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)	T_{max} ($^{\circ}C$)	Hf (mW)
Cotton	102.42	5.62	166.06	1.55	252.02	3.23	326.77	16.05	348.42	11.36	532.64	48.21
Kraftliner basepaper	106.52	2.47	177.27	0.58	211.91	0.78	323.05	7.9	349.4	7.92	532.26	15.53
Testliner basepaper	103.28	0.83	166.25	0.44	233.6	0.71	331.05	7.34	350.98	7.66	531.89	13.03

In Table 3 cotton and different quality of basepapers average results can be seen. The local minimum and maximum points are shown by the temperature ($^{\circ}C$) peaks and the associated heatflow (mW) values. The local points are placed between the inflexion points of the curves. The cotton samples have it's great importance in the experiment due to it has over 90% α -cellulose content, which can be a comparative base of the examinations of basepapers as it can simple define the mechanical and quality properties of the paper. The chemically bonded water departed from the cotton sample at 102.42 $^{\circ}C$. The primary pyrolysis is done between 252.02 $^{\circ}C$ and 348.42 $^{\circ}C$. The secondary pyrolysis is occurred between 348.42 $^{\circ}C$ and 532.64 $^{\circ}C$. After the secondary pyrolysis further reactions are not relevant due to the charring process is

ended. The corresponding heatflow values for the primary pyrolysis is 16.05 mW and for the secondary pyrolysis is 48.21 mW. The Kraftliner basepaper primary pyrolysis is occurred between 211.91 °C and 349.40 °C. The secondary pyrolysis is from 349.40 °C to 532.26°C. The heatflow values are 7.90 mW and 15.53 mW. The Testliner basepaper is a lower quality paper as Kraftliner. The primary pyrolysis is measured between 232.39 °C and 331.05 °C. The secondary pyrolysis is at 350.98 °C and 531.89 °C. The corresponding heatflow values are 7.34 mW for the primary pyrolysis and 13.03 mW at the secondary pyrolysis.

Figure 2: Summary measurements figure (Cotton-black; Kraftliner basepaper-Blue; Resin-red; Kaolin-green; CaCO₃-orange)

The measurements of Kaolin and CaCO₃ can be stated that there are no significant exothermic or endothermic reactions in the experiment range. Based on the literature it's thermal decomposition starts at higher temperature over 550 °C. The resin as a further filler material produces exothermic reaction shown by tendency on the curves which can be observed from 400 °C.

Table 4: Cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin exothermic processes defined by peak temperature (°C) and heatflow (mW)

Material	Significant temperature peaks (°C)	Corresponding heatflow values (mW)
Cellulose	315-400	15-60
Hemicellulose	220-315	5-10
Lignin	900	0-60

5 CONCLUSIONS

Results can be explained that at lower temperature various samples independently behave on similar way, mainly the chemically bonded water leave from each materials around at 100 °C. At higher temperature over 200

°C can be stated that primary pyrolysis of each samples started and ended at around 350 °C. It can be stated that mainly the cellulose content of the samples can be influenced the starting or ending temperature of primer pyrolysis process as the lower cellulose content means lower starting or ending temperature.(Tóth , Koltai and Böröcz, 2018.) The secondary pyrolysis lasts until around 530 °C at each materials due to the cellulose content indicate same total charring process at each samples. However the heatflow values can refer to the cellulose amount of the given sample as at the cotton can be observed higher heatflow values 48.21 mW and at Testliner basepaper 13,03 mW at the end of the secondary pyrolysis. Separating each pyrolysis parts and analyzing the specific range help to understand the behaviour of the samples under a thermoanalytical test, which refer to exact quality and mechanical properties depending on it's cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and filler materials content ratio. (Dr. Sho-ichi Tsujiyama, 2000.; Haiping Y., Hanping Ch., 2006.)

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